

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY IN ANALYSING THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN ENHANCING CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT USING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL (SEM) WITH SPECIAL FOCUS ON INDIAN PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS IN CHENNAI CITY

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Abstract

The banking industry in India is one of the largest in the country and it accounts for 8% of GDP in the country, moreover the total number of current and savings accounts in the banks stood at more than 162 crores in 2020, hence the industry is highly vital for individual and economic development of the country. The social media users in India have been increasing and it is currently at 440 million which accounts for nearly 45% of the total population, hence the banking companies are focusing in using the social media in order to possess better interaction with the customers. Hence, the usage of social media enables the companies in the banking sector to create new avenue in connecting and conversing with the existing and target customers, also support in sharing vital information which will support in adding more value, address the queries on real time basis and generate more revenues.

This study is focused in understanding the role of social media in enhancing the customer engagement in Indian private banking companies, the study is confined to Chennai city and the researchers are focused in using quantitative analysis in order to perform the study effectively. The authors use closed ended questions in order to collect the data from the respondents, who are the customers of the banks, and analyse them using SPSS and AMOS package.

Keywords: social media, Customer engagement, Low-cost advantage, Correlation analysis, Structural equation model.

Introduction

The social media platforms are being deployed with the purpose of assisting the users to enhance the virtual communication through sharing the thoughts, information, ideas and other contents. These aspects have enabled the individuals to use different social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn etc. It has been noted that the total number of social media users across the globe has reached more than 4 billion as of 2021 and the numbers are expected to grow more as many individuals, business and others are focusing in using the potential of social media for broadcasting the information and get connected with their friends, customers etc. In many industries and companies, the management uses social media so as to offer information related to the products and services, focus in connecting with the customers

and converse with the intended customers so as to deliver better value to them, increase customer loyalty and also have better customer engagement in order to achieve sustainable growth and development (Aggrawal, 2019).

In the digital environment, business enterprises focus in applying interactive and creative measures so as to enhance the customers experience towards the products and services. The social media also supports the marketers, management and others to create better impact in the minds of the customers through emotional and cognitive nuance which will support in getting better feedback, make more purchases, refer about the company products and services to their friends and families and support in organisational growth and development (Fernandes, 2019). Hence, it is stated that the term customer engagement refers to enabling the customers and clients to have voluntary involvement, contributions towards the company brand, products and services offered, provide the feedback in the social media group and support the organisation in creating more value to the customer for sustainable advantage. It has been identified by the researchers that the highly engaged customers tend to stay loyal with the brand and influence others in enhancing more sales of the products and services (Colicev, 2018).

In case of banking industry, where they are more involved in offering financial services and other assistance for the customers, the management uses the social media so as to allow the customers to engage effectively, collaborate with the company official, and interact with them in order to solve a specific problem or support in creating better services (Liu, 2019). The implementation of Web 2.0 technologies has resulted in understanding the growing needs and requirements of the customers in the banking space. Hence, many companies in the industry have focused in using the social media which is considered as the perfect platform in enhancing the customer relationship management, the researchers have stated that the social media enables the banks to regain the loyalty and trust of the customers effectively, also enable in attracting new customers at lower cost. In India, many privately banking companies like HDFC, ICICI, Axis Bank, Kotak Mahindra, Yes Bank, IDFC First Bank and others tend to use social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter etc in order to connect with the customers on a real time basis, understand their requirements effectively and offer timely solution so as to deliver better value to them. Moreover, the social media platforms act as a tool to communicate and collaborate with the customers for effective engagement. The management and marketers use social media in order to create groups, space etc so as to communicate critical information, engage the customers, address their queries and also support in cross selling of the products. It has been stated that during the pandemic situations, banking companies are using the social media to build and enhance customer relationship through sharing the information related to contactless payments and services, encourage the customers to actively participate with the management in making key protocols for customer safety thereby supporting customers and nation.

The basic aim of the study is involved in analysing the role of social media in enhancing customer engagement, hence the researchers has framed the critical factors as: use of social media as low-cost advantage in retaining the customers, supporting in sharing data and value

to the customers, addressing customer queries on real time basis, support in enhancing brand value of the company.

Need for the study

The customer engagement through social media is stated as the critical measure of how the management of banking companies are using the social media so as to leverage in interacting with the real customers of the banks, support in understanding the requirements and deliver better value and services to them at low cost. The article is focused in understanding the factors which drives the private banking companies in India in unleashing the potential of social media for better customer engagement so that they can enhance their brand image, support in retaining existing customers and attracting new customers. Hence there is a need for analysing the main determinants in using the social media for better and effective customer engagement.

Review of Literature

In the definition of customer engagement (CE), Vivek (2014) emphasizes the emotional bond between the consumer and the brand, which is a direct consequence of the deepening of a "preventive and favorable mental state" for the consumer. Furthermore, Rahman et al. (2017) reiterates this view and views TC as a "psychological condition that arises in a contact point service relationship as a result of an interactive and co-creative customer experience with the agent / focus object (eg a brand)". Due to this psychological condition, customer engagement can explain behaviors that go beyond the origin of the product and can take many forms, from publishing product reviews online.

McCoy (2018) distinguish the two frameworks by stating that customer engagement versus commitment requires "experience and asset value". Harrigan et al., to support this idea based on tourist brands on social media. Commitment should be placed before CE because "consumers' personal interest and relevance to a brand before engaging in particularly persuasive behavior". Rather et al. (2018) found a positive effect of participation in customer engagement

Commitment reflects a client's desire to maintain a valuable relationship "due to a psychological condition that forces a person to take a specific action". Therefore, the commitment has the potential to influence the perception of future interactions and experiences with marketing objects (Fernandes et.al., (2019)). Thus, it can be assumed that when individuals show commitment, they are much more likely to develop positive attitudes and behaviors towards a particular brand, leading to consumer engagement. Mollen and Palazan et. al., (2019) emphasized their relationship with a commitment to active engagement, where the brand becomes personal in the eyes of consumers. Customer engagement is often expressed in connection with psychological engagement, where customer engagement is seen as the only acceptable alternative in a product category.

The definition of CE is conveyed by emphasizing the customer's lifetime value, which aims to develop long-term buying behavior through recurring purchases, upward trends and cross-

selling, which links CE to loyalty. In addition, the Bowden CE process (Calderón-Monge, 2021) focuses on examining, establishing and developing customer relationships and the mechanisms that lead to brand loyalty. The same idea that links consumer engagement to engagement in the online environment.

Aim and Objectives

The main aim of the study is to analyse the role of social media in enhancing customer engagement in Indian private sector banks in Chennai city.

The objectives can be framed as follows:

To understand use of social media as low-cost advantage in retaining the customers which leads to better customer engagement

To apprehend the importance of sharing data and value to the customers using social media for better engagement of the customers in Indian private banking companies

To measure the nature of addressing customer queries on real time basis support in enhancing customer engagement

To investigate the impact of using social media platforms for enhancing brand value of the company as a means of customer engagement.

Research Methodology

The study is confined in using descriptive research design as it supports the research in understanding in deep the critical role of social media in enhancing customer engagement. The top management and marketers of many industries, including banking and financial services focuses in using the power of social media for gaining competitive advantage through better customer engagement, which will support in enhancing loyalty, repeated purchases and refer more customers to the company. The researchers have applied both primary data source and secondary data source for the study. A detailed closed ended questionnaire is framed and circulated to the respondents, in order to understand the role of social media in enhancing the customer engagement in Indian private banking companies with focus in Chennai city, nearly 162 respondents were chosen through convenience sampling method. The authors also use published journals, dissertation, third party report and online resources like Google Scholar to gather secondary data for performing the study. The data is being analysed using SPSS and AMOS in order to arrive at meaningful interpretation for the study.

Analysis and Interpretation

The data analysis is performed so as to understand the demographic composition of the respondents, enable in analysing the role of social media in supporting customer engagement and to test the hypothesis of the study effectively.

Frequency analysis

Table 1: Demographic analysis

GENDER	Frequency	Percent
Male	140	86.4
Female	22	13.6
AGE	Frequency	Percent
Less than 30 Years	32	19.8
31 - 40 Years	74	45.7
41 - 50 Years	25	15.4
Above 50 Years	31	19.1
QUALIFICATION	Frequency	Percent
Completed UG program	33	20.4
Completed PG program	61	37.7
Completed Professional program	40	24.7
Others	28	17.3
MARITAL STATUS	Frequency	Percent
Single	64	39.5
Married	98	60.5
BANK	Frequency	Percent
ICICI Bank	68	42
HDFC Bank	59	36.4
Axis Bank	23	14.2
Others	12	7.4
WORK EXPERIENCE	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 Years	34	21
5 - 10 Years	72	44.4
10 - 15 Years	29	17.9
More than 15 Years	27	16.7
Total	162	100

Based on demographic analysis as presented in table 1 it is noted that 86.4% of the respondents were male and remaining were female, 45.7% of them were in the age group between 31 - 40 Years, 19.8% were in the age group of less than 30 years, 19.1% were above 50 years and remaining were in the age group between 41 - 50 Years. 37.7% of the respondents have completed PG program, 24.7% have completed professional course, 20.4% were undergraduate and remaining have completed other courses like ITI / Diploma etc. 60.5% of the respondents were married, 42% of the respondents were having their bank account in ICICI, 36.4% were associated with HDFC, 14.2% are with Axis and remaining were with other private banking companies. 44.4% of the respondents possess 5 - 10 Years of experience, 17.9% were having experience between 10 - 15 Years, and 16.7% were having more than 15 years of experience.

Correlation analysis

The next part of the analysis is involved in measure the degree of association between the independent variables viz., Low-Cost Advantage; Sharing Data and Value; Addressing Customer Queries and Enhancing Brand Value with the dependent variable: Better Customer Engagement.

Table 2: Correlation analysis

Correlation Coefficient	Low-Cost Advantage	Sharing Data and Value	Addressing Customer Queries	Enhancing Brand Value	Better Customer Engagement
Low-Cost Advantage	1	.835**	.844**	.858**	.832**
Sharing Data and Value	.835**	1	.859**	.856**	.900**
Addressing Customer Queries	.844**	.859**	1	.873**	.838**
Enhancing Brand Value	.858**	.856**	.873**	1	.872**
Better Customer Engagement	.832**	.900**	.838**	.872**	1

The analysis reveals that the nature of correlation between all the independent and dependent variables are more than +0.800, hence there exist better relationship among them. The highest correlation lies between Sharing Data and Value and Better Customer Engagement with +0.900, the next is between enhancing brand value and Better Customer Engagement with +0.873.

Test of Hypothesis

The next section of the analysis is involved in testing the hypothesis of the study, the researcher uses Chi square test in order to measure if there is any significant difference between the variables.

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no significant difference among use of social media as low-cost advantage in retaining the customers and better customer engagement.

Table 3: Chi square analysis among low-cost advantage and customer engagement

Low-cost advantage	Value	df	P Val.
Chi-Square	282.930a	16	0.00
LR	241.283	16	0.00
Linear-by-Linear	111.413	1	0.00

From Chi square analysis of table 3, it is noted that P value is 0.00 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 (Signi at 5%), hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference among use of social media as low-cost advantage in retaining the customers and better customer engagement.

Hypothesis 2

H0: There is no significant difference among importance of sharing data and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Table 4: Chi square analysis among sharing data and value and customer engagement

Sharing data and value	Value	df	P Val.
Chi-Square	331.740a	16	0.00
LR	260.041	16	0.00
Linear-by-Linear	130.453	1	0.00

From Chi square analysis of table 4, it is noted that P value is 0.00 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 (Signi at 5%), hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference among importance of sharing data and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Hypothesis 3

H0: There is no significant difference among addressing customer queries on real time basis and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Table 5: Chi square analysis among addressing customer queries on real time basis and customer engagement

Addressing customer queries	Value	df	P Val.
Chi-Square	182.207a	16	0.00
LR	189.006	16	0.00
Linear-by-Linear	113.186	1	0.00

From Chi square analysis of table 5, it is noted that P value is 0.00 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 (Signi at 5%), hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference among addressing customer queries on real time basis and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Hypothesis 4

H0: There is no significant difference among addressing customer queries on real time basis and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Table 6: Chi square analysis among addressing customer queries on real time basis and customer engagement

Addressing customer queries	Value	df	P Val.
Chi-Square	182.207a	16	0.00
LR	189.006	16	0.00
Linear-by-Linear	113.186	1	0.00

From Chi square analysis of table 6, it is noted that P value is 0.00 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 (Signi at 5%), hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference among addressing customer queries on real time basis and value to the customers and better customer engagement.

Hypothesis 5

H0: There is no significant difference among enhancing brand value and better customer engagement.

Table 7: Chi square analysis among enhancing brand value and customer engagement

Enhancing brand value	Value	df	P Val.
Chi-Square	275.265a	16	0.00
LR	242.947	16	0.00
Linear-by-Linear	122.465	1	0.00

From Chi square analysis of table 7, it is noted that P value is 0.00 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 (Signi at 5%), hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference among enhancing brand value and better customer engagement.

Structural Equation Model

The application of SEM in the data analysis supports the study in making a critical understanding involving factor analysis and multiple regression analysis. The application of path diagram states the major relationship among the variables and state in quantifiable terms between them.

Fig 1: Path Analysis of Customer Engagement

The above path analysis shows that the independent variables possess positive relation towards the dependent variable.

Table 8: SEM analysis

SEM Results
Minimum was achieved
Chi-square = 1040.466
Degrees of freedom = 62
Probability level = .000

Dependent	Independent	Est, Val	P Val
Customer Engagement	Low-Cost Advantage	0.136	0.00
Customer Engagement	Sharing Data and Value	0.568	0.00
Customer Engagement	Addressing Customer Queries	0.088	0.03
Customer Engagement	Enhancing Brand Value	0.344	0.00

From the analysis the chi square value is 1040.466 and hence the model is stated to be good fit, also the p value between the variables is less than 0.05 and hence concluded that there exist better association between the independent and dependent variables.

The Indian banking sector is one of the largest in the country and accounts for 8% of the country's GDP, and the number of checking and savings accounts in banks exceeded 162 million by 2020, making the sector extremely important for individuals. And the country's economic development. The number of social media users in India has grown to 440 million, representing almost 45% of the total population, which is why banking companies focus on using social media to better interact with customers. Therefore, the use of social media allows banking companies to create new ways to connect and chat with existing and targeted customers, and to support the exchange of important information that adds even more value, to answer real-time questions. Finances and generates more revenue. The number of social media users worldwide is estimated to reach 4 billion by 2021, and this number is expected to grow even more as many individuals, companies and others focus on spreading potential social media. Information and keep in touch with friends, customers and more. In many industries and companies, management uses social media to provide information about products and services, to focus on interacting and talking with customers, to give them better value, increase customer loyalty and increase customer engagement. . Growth and sustainable development. Management and marketers use social media for groups, websites and so on. To create. Communicate important information, attract customers, answer questions and support cross-selling of products. It has been reported that in pandemic situations, banking companies use social media to build and improve customer relationships, share payment information and contactless services, and encourage customers to actively participate with management in developing security protocols. Thus supporting customers and the nation.

Conclusion

In the banking industry, where they are more involved in providing financial services and other types of customer assistance, management uses social media to enable customers to effectively communicate, interact, interact and manage with a particular company to solve the problem. or help create better services. The use of Web 2.0 technology has helped to understand the growing needs and demands of customers in the banking field. As a result, many companies in the industry have focused on the use of social media, which is considered an ideal platform for improving customer relationship management. Researchers say that social media is an effective way for banks to regain customer trust. They also allow you to attract new customers at a lower cost.

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